

"CREATIVE APPROACH OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS"

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the importance of the teacher's creative approach in the assimilation of mathematical concepts by primary school students. The creative approach is considered as the main factor in developing students' logical thinking, problem-solving skills, and increasing their interest in mathematics. The article highlights the methodological methods and pedagogical conditions for implementing a creative approach.

Introduction

One of the main tasks facing the education system today is to equip students not only with knowledge, but also with the ability to think creatively and solve unusual problems. Primary education, especially mathematics lessons, is the fundamental basis for the formation of these skills. In a situation where traditional teaching methods do not arouse interest in students, the teacher's creative approach serves as a decisive factor in improving the quality of education.

A creative approach is understood as the teacher's application of non-standard, new, effective teaching methods, didactic materials, and educational technologies.

Creative thinking is the ability of an individual to unusually creatively solve their goals and objectives, as well as to search for more effective ways to achieve their goals for intellectual development. That is, creativity is mainly the ability to learn and correctly apply unusual ideas that are unlike other people in everyday life, to add standard thinking that has become a tradition, and to know ways to quickly solve various problem situations that we encounter in our lives. The characteristic of creativity consists of the integration of psychological qualities and independent thinking abilities, which lay the foundation for the formation of creative abilities in the individual [1. B. 21.].

Teacher creativity: The teacher must abandon ready-made templates in their work and create unique methods that meet the individual needs of each student.

Motivation and interest: The creative approach shows that mathematics is not just a collection of dry rules, but an interesting world and increases the student's internal motivation.

Development of logical and non-traditional thinking: The teacher develops divergent (branched) thinking in students by presenting simple arithmetic problems in the form of life tasks and logical puzzles.

Creative methods and technologies in teaching mathematics

Primary school teachers can use the following methods for creative teaching of mathematics:

Game activity and didactic games

Role-playing games: To develop students' skills in counting money and working with units of measurement in real life by giving them the roles of shopkeeper and accountant.

Numerical labyrinths and puzzles: Interesting logic problems solved by performing mathematical operations.

Quantification games: Calculating, comparing, and grouping numbers using objects in a class.

We believe that the main focus in the development of students' creative competencies can be formed as follows:

scientific substantiation of the essence of the features of the concept of "creative competence," which scientifically implies the presence of creative abilities and intellectual thinking potential;

ability to develop new ideas in correctly finding solutions to problematic situations;

to correctly navigate various problematic pedagogical situations arising in the educational process;

the ability to correctly adapt to pedagogical changes and non-standard situations arising in the educational process;

creation of pedagogical and psychological conditions for the development of students' creative competence during classes, including a favorable pedagogical and psychological climate in the student community for the development of a creative spirit;

development of problem-based pedagogical situations that allow for the development of focus, learning, and logical thinking during the training process;

proper design of the system of independent work on the development of students' creative competence [2. P. 18-22.].

It is known that a person remembers 10% of what they hear, 50% of what they see, and 90% of what they do independently, therefore the most effective form of learning is practical work. Modern information technologies provide great opportunities, including the possibility of modeling various experiences through information modeling, and therefore, as a rule, do not require large expenditures of material resources. [3. B. 386-389.].

Large-scale studies have been conducted on the study of the pedagogical features of effective interaction between students and computers. However, the specific pedagogical features of teaching and developing students' creative competencies in an information technology environment have not been specifically studied. Therefore, the introduction of special use of computer technologies and software capabilities in this area fully meets modern requirements. Ignoring or rejecting these characteristics leads to a sharp decrease in the efficiency of existing computer programs. Analysis of blind research shows that the process of teaching creative-thinking students is characterized by specific pedagogical features. Usually,

students who think creatively need no less attention and psychological-pedagogical support than their peers and classmates. In this case, students demonstrate a high degree of independence in the process of perceiving educational material. As a specific pedagogical factor indicating the presence of various abilities in students, they emphasize the ability to independently study new educational material presented to students. Expansion of opportunities for the realization of abilities, the student's independent learning and its development

the development of computer-based special educational programs and the control of theoretical and scientific knowledge corresponds to the principle of individualization of education, which is important in computerization, psychological support of students, and pedagogical education. The development of creative abilities in traditional educational programs, designed for the full acquisition of theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and abilities, is considered a secondary issue. Our research shows that this approach cannot be used in teaching creative students, as it negatively affects the psychological development of students [4. - 296 p.]

Creative use of information and communication technologies

Interactive programs: Special mathematical game applications, visualization of concepts through animated videos.

"Virtual travel": Using videos depicting real objects to explore topics such as geometric shapes and units of measurement.

Problem-based learning and heuristic methods

Question "Why is this so?": Encourage students to independently search for the origin of a rule or formula.

Project approach: Organization of small projects requiring mathematical knowledge (for example, "Drawing a classroom plan," "Calculating the family budget").

Expected results of the creative approach

The implementation of a creative approach in practice will lead to the following positive results:

Knowledge reinforcement: Students remember for a long time what they have learned without being forced to memorize.

Development of logical thinking: The ability to consider multiple options in problem-solving is formed.

Enhancement of mathematical competence: Students learn to apply mathematics in everyday life.

Strengthening the teacher's authority: The teacher becomes not a transmitter of knowledge, but a mentor who organizes creative activity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the creative approach of primary school teachers to teaching mathematics is a requirement of today. This approach makes the learning process interesting, effective, and goal-oriented. Teachers themselves must constantly engage in creative research, experiment with new methods, and improve their pedagogical skills. The younger generation, having studied mathematics through a creative approach, will grow into mature individuals capable of solving complex problems in the future..

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